

THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION IN THE WORLD AND IN UZBEKISTAN; PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

¹Tulibaev Khikmatulla Egamovich, ²Rasulova Barno

¹History teacher of the 9th secondary school in the town of Yangiyol, honorary professor of the Turan Academy of Sciences,

²A senior teacher of English at the 9th secondary school of The town of Yangiyol

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117336>

Abstract. *The article focuses on the globalization and particularly its effect and footprints in Uzbekistan and its different life spheres. The article discusses novelties derived from the situation appeared after globalization spread and fast paced changes resulted by it and responses in the country towards them. Moreover, problems caused by globalization and its spread and their practical solutions carried out in the country.*

Keywords: *globalization, business, culture, economics, socio-political crises, nationalism.*

The 21st century is the age of technology, the period of integration and mutual cooperation of the world community. Today the formation of the united geopolitical area in the world and the process of common globalization is rapidly developing.

Well, it is natural to ask what is the meaning of the term "globalization". In this regard, many political scientists and politicians expressed their opinions and concepts.

In fact, the term "globalization" is considered comparatively new in political science. To be more precise about forty years ago, in 1983, the American political scientist T. Levitta published his article in "Harvard Business Review" where this term was firstly used. Globalization usually means a process that characterizes the change in form and essence of economic, technological, political and cultural relations in the world as a result of the acceleration of international trade.

What are the taken measures and the role of our economic and political zone in today's globalization processes, what consequences can this lead to, what is the meaning of the word globalization in general? We will try to find answers to such questions.

The new term was given a wider meaning at Harvard Business School. The main propagator of this term is the researcher of this school, the Japanese scientist K. Ohmae, who published the book "The borderless world." in 1990, Globalization is defined in the UN Human Development Report as follows:

Globalization is the ongoing integration of the world economy due to the expansion of the flow of goods, services, capital, labor and ideas, as well as the joint efforts of countries to solve global economic problems.

Today, both positive and negative sides of globalization are becoming increasingly apparent. There is no doubt that the last few decades of the previous millennium will be marked in the history of mankind by the further strengthening of international relations, the profound integration and increasing interdependence of the countries of the world. Currently the influence area of the countries on each other are expanding, the events happening in one part of the world may have an immediate effect in other parts. The states of Wars between Russia and Ukraine, Israel and Palestine; other socio-political crises, the anger and protest of the people of the world against the death of thousands of innocent people, the growth in the calls to fight together to mend these situations proves our view.

Therefore, all the people of the world including politicians and heads of state and ordinary citizens living in different countries constantly observe events and changes happening on a global scale with great interest and monitor them, being aware of every situation they try to analyze economic and political processes based on their own benefits.

The political, economic and social changes taking place in the world are so closely connected that it is possible to observe global processes that affect individuals, society and states in all aspects of life.

The 21st century will decidedly be the century when the whole world will be involved in international relations. In such conditions, the process of integration, the process of expanding the participation of sovereign states in international institutions and organizations should be considered not only as a requirement of history, but as a powerful factor of stability as well.

Globalization, that is world integration, can be regarded as a process of growth; as an important factor in the political, economic and social life of the peoples of the world, which determines the development of our planet in the new millennium, creating a turn-point in the history of mankind. Today, the processes of globalization are intensifying in the world, and new threats and dangers against peace and stability are increasing more and more. Such a complex and dangerous situation calls for a critical evaluation of the work done in the field and improvement of its activities based on the requirements of the times [4].

Another definition of the term globalization is that this process in short means creating a huge united society on earth by strengthening the mutual relations of all economic systems in the world, further developing interstate economic, political, and trade relations.

It is appropriate to raise questions about the position of our region, in particular, Uzbekistan, in this huge society and how Uzbekistan will benefit from such integration. In our opinion, the following cases, which are striking manifestations of globalization, are important for strengthening international stability in the new millennium, as well as for faster integration of Uzbekistan into the world community:

- globalization creates a basis for the acceleration of the process of global economic growth by eliminating trade barriers and incrementing the flow of commercial goods and information;

- this further strengthens international and interstate ties. By ensuring that no part of the world is free from the critical gaze of the media, globalization widely promotes the principles of freedom and human rights.

- another reason for the popularity of globalization is the emergence of an international agreement based on the principles of constitutional democracy, free market and the preservation of human rights and values that are common to all mankind;

- countries that violate these values will face not only political, but also economic pressure on them through market structures;

The acceleration of the globalization process also has actions upon the development of science and cultures, based on the laws of interconnection and dialectics of interaction.

Of course, globalization also has its own negative aspects. Considering that this is a separate research topic, it can be said that in different parts of the world, doubts and uncertainty about the process of globalization leading to some form of cultural and economic dominance, as well as to the spirit of nationalism, have already formed.

If we give the issue intensive study, we may notice that globalization can have positive effects for human development as well as negative consequences, and they are as follows:

- First of all, the negative consequences of this process are that due to the fact that Western countries have advanced in the field of technological advancements, both the reserves and the economic activities of our planet can be controlled by multinational corporations that are developing and becoming stronger on a global scale.

This situation increases the risk of reckless wasting of resources for their own benefit, the transition of the management systems of many countries to such large transnational corporations. Secondly, globalization does not make it easier to achieve social equality in the world, on the contrary, it makes it more difficult.

- thirdly, countries that could not withstand the onslaught of global economic processes and for a long time could not stop being the “lower level” of the world found themselves under the threat of serious social and civil conflicts. Vivid examples of this are the ongoing localism in African countries, civil wars, insurrections, instability in a number of countries in Asia and Latin America. Such a risk is real for countries in transition, like the countries in the Caucasus and Central Asia.

- fourthly, the uneven economic and social development in the world increases the transition of international military conflicts from the poorest countries to the richest. The severity of the economic situation, the slow progress of democratic processes and other social and political situations have caused the migration of many qualified and intelligent personnel to Russia and Germany, the USA and other countries. This situation also applies to our region.

- fifthly, global processes connected with the emergence of mafia structures and terrorist groups, including transnational criminal activities which include criminal wealth to any goods that bring large profits, from weapons and drugs to human organs, are intensifying.

All this explains the reason why people not only in developing but also in developed countries are wary of the process of globalization. At the moment, the consistent continuation of a well-thought-out tight monetary policy is seen as an important issue for job creation [5].

But globalization cannot be avoided, it is a historical process in the progress of society. But an important task of humanity is preventing globalization from having a negative impact on certain elements and structures in the society.

The need to know the basic principles of the correct entry of Uzbekistan into the global development system is as follows:

The strategic goal of Uzbekistan should be considered the desire to avoid the fate of joining the world system only as an integral part of its resource and raw material complex, to achieve equal rights in the global market. Of course, this is not easy to achieve. To solve this problem it is necessary to create the following conditions:

- strive to be among the leaders in the field of information technology development;
- Implementation of structural reforms of the economy in order to create a progressive model directly oriented to the world market in terms of technical, technological, organizational and economic aspects, and in practice, introducing the modern technologies of this country;
- create a industrial structure capable competing with the world's leading manufacturers not only in the national but also in the foreign market. Establishing the national financial market and its integration into the world financial system, conduct a well-thought-out policy in the areas of home anti-monopoly.

From considering what has been analyzed and discussed above it can be inferred that it should be noted that it is necessary to create conditions for achieving the maximum positive results

from globalization and try to reduce its negative consequences to a minimum level. The basis of such a system is the establishment of equal cooperation between countries and dynamic renewal in this area.

REFERENCES

1. Anan K. "Millennium Report of the United Nations" 2000
2. Globalization and human development. UN Bulletin 2013
3. Ohmae K. "Borderless World" M. 1991
4. T. Mamatqabilov, Sh. Mirabdullaeva, I. Polatov, D. Sayfullayeva **OVERCOMING GLOBAL PROBLEMS AND DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES** // SAI. 2023. №B10. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/overcoming-global-problems-and-development-strategies> (дата обращения: 09.11.2023).
5. Khusenov, T. Khafizov, T. Mamatqabilov, D. Sayfullayeva **KEY TRENDS IN SUPPLY PEACE AND RESTORATION** // SAI. 2023. №B10. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/key-trends-in-supply-peace-and-restoration> (дата обращения: 09.11.2023).